

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-134-IG-1% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	13	Acq. Method Set:	1%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	4 134
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/19/2022 2:52:30 PM CST		
Date Processed:	6/23/2023 11:04:28 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	12.226	264985	21.06	13569
2	13.458	355991	28.29	14961
3	14.581	372243	29.58	16341
4	17.873	265296	21.08	9634

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-85-IG-1% ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20221119
Vial:	1	Acq. Method Set:	1%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 85
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	20.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/19/2022 8:51:24 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 5:18:22 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	11.873	128807	6.88	6998
2	12.944	1579123	84.40	70452
3	14.152	109477	5.85	4955
4	17.304	53620	2.87	2251